

'Itu Puja': A Traditional Culture in Sundarbans and Sustainability

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Traditional culture embodies the spiritual essence and serves as a civilizational symbol for a notion, a society or a specific group of people. People maintain their own traditional culture through generations in unchanged form and thus bear their own customs, beliefs, rituals and history. Currently, when the world is facing great challenges against global warming, climate change, and rapid biodiversity loss, all focus is centered on “sustainability”. One of the best remedies for maintaining sustainability is to lightning the valuable Traditional culture. Locals of the world heritage site Sundarbans maintain several traditions where women are an important part. Women maintain various Household worships, like *Mangal Chandi Broto*, *Sitol Sasthi*, *Ashok Sasthi*, *Chapra Sasthi*, *Itu puja*, and more like this. *Itu Puja* is the worship of God Sun and Maa Laxmi, where people pray for well-being, good agricultural production and fertility. The objectives of the study to explore traditional rituals related to *Itu puja* and find out relations with sustainability, if any. Data collected by individual interviews from local women who are attached to *Itu Puja*. After thematic analysis, it has been found that traditional rituals related to *Itu Puja* are linked to environmental, social and economic sustainability.

Keywords: Traditional culture, sustainability, sundarbans, household worship

Presently, the Earth is going through one of the largest phases of biodiversity loss and its effect is unpredictable. According to a United Nations report, the rate of extinction of nature by humans is a hundred times higher than the natural causes rate in the past and in the near future it can be thousands times higher (Arora, 2018). So, for secure the future generations, the most important thing for human beings is to maintain sustainability. One of the critical ways of maintaining sustainability is to give importance to traditional culture, valuable indigenous practices, and the community who are very close to nature. In traditional communities or societies, natural resources management occurred in a sustainable way by traditional local cultures and intimate connections with nature that sustain them (Negi, 2010). There are several strategies embedded in traditional cultures that are able to safeguard the valuable biodiversity (Rathoure, 2024) as well as sustainability.

Biodiversity-rich Sundarbans, which was declared as the world heritage site by UNESCO (Srivastava, 2025) in 1987 not only an ecological wonder but also enriched with unique traditional cultures that have been passed down verbally generation after generation. The cyclone-prone area, Sundarbans, is an abode of the Royal Bengal tiger (*Panthera tigris tigris*), Crocodile, snake, and other animals, making the area fearful for living of human beings (Karmakar, 2019). Locals of Sundarbans struggle continuously in their daily livelihood and to survive, they keep faith in God and the Goddess. People's beliefs in local God and Goddess - Maa Bonbibi, Kalu Roy, Maa Manosa, Maa Laxmi, and so on. In many households,

worship is performed by women. *Itu puja* is such a household worship performed by unmarried and married women in Sundarbans (Sen, 1995). *Itu puja* is a tradition that bears the belief, rituals, and customs through generations (Das & Lakra, 2025). Also, the traditional rituals related to *Itu puja* show positive effects on sustainability.

Review of Literature

Traditional Culture

The traditional culture of a nation serves as the spiritual home, preserving ancestral wisdom and encompassing civilization experiences (Lyu, 2024). The traditional culture of a region or nation bears its history, thinking patterns, values, customs, and cultural traditions (Lyu, 2024; Wang, 2023). Also, for a unique identity and cultural confidence, culture serves as a vital source of a nation (Lyu, 2024). Traditional cultures are more generic and form the best social, legal, economic and artistic models that are accepted by time and experiences (Kostina, 2022). However, with the rapid progression of modernization as well as globalization, valuable traditional cultures are mostly facing challenges of marginalization, extinction and rapid loss (Wang, 2023). But today, traditional culture is valuable to the world; it shows not only the way of sustainability but also conserves nature in its own way.

Traditional Culture Related to Sustainability

Traditional cultures possess sophisticated knowledge of their environment, frequently expressed through art and traditions (Singh & Singh, 2024). In an era when the world is grappling with a pressing environmental crisis (Joshi, 2021) it is important to preserve the traditional knowledge and cultures (Singh & Singh, 2024). Currently, the space given to traditional culture and knowledge has widened (Mishra, 2018). Traditional lifestyle practices rooted in ancient wisdom it offers valuable insights for a sustainable livelihood (Das, 2023). Cultural beliefs, traditions, and practices influence scientific inquiry and shape research priorities. In India,

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traditional culture is strongly interlinked with climate sustainability (Mondal & Pandey, 2022), environmental conservation (Joshi, 2021), agricultural sustainability (Bajpai, 2024) social sustainability, and so on.

In India, locals of Sundarbans adapted themselves to a harsh climatic environment through their experiences, beliefs, and rituals, generation after generation. Traditionally, transferring culture boosts them to live peacefully and maintain sustainability.

Locals of Sundarbans and the Traditions

Sundarbans, the largest stretch of riverine mangrove forest, extends over the two countries, Bangladesh and India. The Indian Sundarbans encompasses a vast deltaic area where the Ganga and Brahmaputra, two giant rivers of India, meet and disappear in the Bay of Bengal (Jamal et al., 2022). The region forms a complex network of mangrove forest with a criss-cross of numerous estuaries and creeks, which supports a rich biodiversity (Datta et al., 2024) with various types of flora and fauna. Ecologically enriched Sundarbans is the lifeline of a large number of populations who living harmony in the lap of nature for generations (Jamal et al., 2022).

In the Indian Sundarbans, out of 102 islands, only 54 are inhabited by human civilization, where about 4.5 million people live, and the rest of the mangrove forest area (Mitra & Biswas, 2021). To survive in the Sundarbans islands, inhabitants have to fight against a harsh environment as well as have to depend on rich forest biodiversity for their existence. People have respected the forest from immemorial time (Jamal et al., 2022). Locals' livelihood reflects in their traditional cultures through songs, art, myths, and religions (Karmakar, 2019). People mainly engaged in honey collection, crab collection, fishing, cultivation, animal husbandry, and daily labour work for their livelihood (Majumder, 2024). For forest-dependent work, tiger attacks, crocodile attacks in water, pirates attack are the dangerous life risk barriers for the people, whereas storms and floods are common in this region that effects whole environment, including inhabitants. In this adverse environment, people live based on their faith and believe in various gods and goddesses and uphold their primary duty to give protection and preservation of the mangrove forest (Jamal et al., 2022). Men and women are worshippers of the forest deity Maa Bonbibi (Chakrabarty, 2021; Karmakar, 2019) snake deity Maa Manosa, Crocodile God Kalu Roy (Khakon, 2015) and so on. Also, women perform various household worships like *Sitol Sasthi*, *Ashok Sasthi*, *Chapra Sasthi*, *Mangal Chandi Broto*, *Itu puja*, and more like this (Das & Lakra, 2025). *Itu puja* is performed by married and unmarried women and mainly worships the Sun and Goddess Laxmi.

Objectives of the Study

- To explore the traditional cultures (viz., used ingredients, season of worship, rituals, practices, etc.) maintained by women in *Itu Puja* in Sundarbans.
- To find out the link between the explored traditional culture during *Itu puja* and sustainability.

Method

A qualitative method was followed to fulfill the objectives of the study.

Selection of the Study Area

The study area was conducted in the Sundarbans, West Bengal,

India. There are two districts in Sundarbans South 24 Parganas and North 24 Parganas. In the district South 24 Parganas, the Gosaba block was selected purposively, then three villages-Arampur, Jelepara, and Gosaba were selected randomly, where people mainly depend on Agriculture and forest resources for their livelihood.

Participants

A total of twelve ($n=12$) participants were recruited who are residents of the Sundarbans region. Only females are selected who have direct experience to do 'Itu Puja'. Samples are selected purposively based on experiences. Among the total ($n=12$) participants, nine ($n=9$) were married and three ($n=3$) were unmarried women. Participants were aged between 16 years and 71 years from the Hindu religion.

Selection Criteria of the sample

Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Only a permanent resident whose family has resided in Sundarbans for at least 40 years.	A resident whose family lives in the Sundarbans is less than 40 years old.
Only females are included.	Male or other gendered excluded.
Females who directly participant of <i>Itu Puja</i> .	Females not direct participant Excluded.
Females only from the Hindu community are included.	Females from the Muslim, Christian, or other community excluded.

Data Collection and Procedure

To collect data, a semi-structured interview was conducted. A mixed questionnaire with closed and open ended question questionnaire was used to collect information. Each interview was organized based on the participant's favorable time, and the participants were allowed to deviate from the main interview schedule so that they could share new experiences outside of the fixed schedule.

The collected data were analyzed using the qualitative content and thematic analysis process.

Results and Discussion

Itu Puja: A Tradition of Worshipping Nature

Itu Puja is the worship of Surya, or the Sun, and Goddess Laxmi. The word 'Itu' has evolved from Mitu, which is a shortened form of Mitra, i.e., Sun. The puja is performed for the auspiciousness of the human life- agricultural prosperity, fertility, and family well-being. Even a hundred years ago, the *Itu Puja* was practiced in the Sundarbans (Das, 2025). A 69-year-old married woman stated that-

"I get the puja at the age of 16 years from my Mother-in-law, and till now I maintain all rituals for Itu puja."

As per traditional culture, any married or unmarried woman can start *Itu puja* at any age, but it needs to continue her whole life until death, or after transferring it to her daughter or daughter -in-law, can stop the puja.

Season of Puja

The puja is performed for one month. It starts on the last day of the Bengali month Kartik and ends in the eighth month of the Bengali calendar, i.e., Agrahan month. Every Sunday of this month, the worshippers maintain some rituals and make a prayer. A 54 years old women stated that-

"We have to maintain the rituals from Kartik sankranti (i.e., last day of the month) to sankranti of Agrahan month, including 4 or 5 Sundays."

Primary Ingredients Required to Worship

Two earthen pots, mud, five types of cereals-Paddy, Mustard seeds, Gram, Peas, and wheat/pulse; various types of plant twigs, fruits, flowers, and rice dust.

Rituals are Maintained in Itu Puja

Arrangement of Puja. The *Itu puja*, mainly performed by women, including married and unmarried, belongs to the Hindu religion. Women make prayer individually or in groups in a common place. Worshippers make a small structure with mud, like a mud bed, and on it they put two small earthen pots full of water. Then they spread eight types of seeds like mustard seed, peas, grams, paddy seeds, etc., on the mud bed and put various types of twigs like special type of paddy twigs, Durba (*Cynodon dactylon*), Water spinach (*Ipomoea aquatic*) twigs, twigs of Kansira or Bengal day flower (*Commelina benghalensis*) in the earthen pot. A 61-year-old woman stated that-

"We use five types of cereals and various plant twigs in Itu puja".

Also, women use various flowers to arrange the earthen pot and the mud bed. They make *alpona*, i.e., hand-drawing decorative patterns with rice paste batter on the floor of the worship spot. They use rice, molasses, and milk to make paramanno or payesh and offer it to the God and Goddess. Thus, for one month each Sunday, women maintain *Itu Puja* with offering fruits and flowers, while maintaining the rituals. A 47-year-old married woman stated-

"Each Sunday of the whole month of Agrahan, we worship in a group in the yard of my neighbour, where we make Itu Puja. Also, eight other women, including 3 unmarried girls, join to make a prayer".

Continuation of Rituals. Four or five Sundays in the Agrahana month, women perform the puja. Each Sunday, watered the earthen pot with fresh water and replaced it with new plant twigs in the earthen pots, offering flowers, fruit, and sweets to the goddess. In case of group worshipping, a woman reads *Itu's Bratakatha* (a tale of *Itu Puja*), and others listen with a flower and durba in their hand. For the individual, the worshipper read the *bratakatha*. A 56-year-old woman stated that-

"We read Itu's bratakatha at the end of the pooja every Sunday, and it must be the end of the day. Without reading or listening to bratakatha, the pooja remains incomplete".

Rituals at the end of the *Itu puja*. Within one month, the seeds that were spread on the mud bed transferred to plants, and were growing fast. On the last day of the worship, i.e., in the Sankranti of Agrahan month, women make worship and take the earthen pots and abandon them in the pond water. And all worshippers give the blessed food of the goddess to the neighbors. In the blessing food, rice pan cake is mandatory and must be eaten by worshippers after making a prayer. As per a 16-year-old girl-

"I started Itu puja from the age of 10 years with my neighbours' aunts, and I enjoy it a lot. In this puja not need for a priest, a totally women-centric puja, and we directly offer everything to God and Goddess. I arrange all required plant twigs every Sunday for all worshippers in our group".

Analysis

The rituals and practices maintained in *Itu puja* teach to respect and

love nature as well as the way of a sustainable lifestyle. The rituals are linked with sustainability-

Theme 1. Environmental Sustainability Related to the Traditional Itu Puja.

Now a days Environmental sustainability is one of the biggest issues faced by mankind in the whole world. The rapid increase in the human population and, in parallel, an increase in per capita consumption, have placed immense pressure on the natural resources of the planet. Due to the effects of human activities, natural resources are overexploited, contaminated with toxic chemicals, and are difficult for the survival of future generations (Arora, 2018). In this scenario of the world, a small group of women in Sundarbans preserves nature with their traditions- the traditions of beliefs, rituals, customs, and prayers.

In *Itu puja*, the worshipper honours the puja to the Sun as God, respecting the role of the Sun in crop ripening and life-giving energy. *Itu puja* time, i.e., the crop harvesting time in Agrahan month and alternatively as a main part of *Itu puja* women use 5 types of cereals on the mud bed which grow for one month under their nurturing and then they immerse it in the pond or river that reflection of return of nature's gift to the earth the concept stimulates the way to achieve environmental sustainability and secure the future generation. Also in *itu puja*, various types of plant twigs are used, like water spinach (*Ipomoea aquatic*), which has great nutritional value, with rich content of vitamins A, C, iron, calcium, potassium, and phosphorus (Yazhini, 2024). Durba (*Cynodon dactylon*) is also used as a traditional medicine. Juice of Durba is used to stop bleeding, against fever, dysentery, diarrhea, and so many other remedies (Tripathi et al., 2025). *Commelina benghalensis* (Benghal dayflower) is used as folk medicine to prevent and treat various diseases like burns, fever, jaundice, leprosy, snakebite, and headache (Sivvakumar, 2023). Another used twig paddy is the most important crop; rice from paddy is the staple food (Kumar & Seshadri, 2024) in Sundarbans as well as in India (Kumbha, 2022).

Here, all plant parts and cereals that are used in *Itu puja* are conserved by the locals of Sundarbans with respect, and thus, locals of Sundarbans conserve the environment as well as maintain sustainability.

Theme 2. Social Sustainability Related to the Rituals of Itu Puja

A vital pillar of sustainability is social sustainability. It mainly focuses on human well-being and improvement of the quality of life (Wang et al., 2024). Giving more priority to family and other personal relationships is one of the vital causes of being fine or well-being (Gasper, 2004). Women in Sundarbans organize *Itu Puja* generally in groups, and for one month, they maintain all rituals and make prayers together. Thus, traditional cultures make a strong bond of togetherness, social cohesion, and improve human well-being as well as quality of life. Also, *Itu puja* is fully women-controlled without any male priest; it bears the message of women's freedom and empowerment. Thus, social bonding and women's empowerment are imposed towards social sustainability.

Theme 3. Economic Sustainability and Itu Puja.

Agriculture is the key sector in the economy of any nation. Its contribution towards employment, food security, and Gross Domestic Product needs emphasis on its production and

consumption (Kumar & Seshadri, 2024). In *Itu puja*, women pray to *Itu* or *Maa Laxmi* for better and profitable crop production that includes high-yielding with reduced input cost, resource efficacy, and market stability. Thus, the prayer reflects positivity in economic sustainability.

Conclusion

Traditional culture is generally centered on local gods and goddess; make connection between everyday human life and the divine. For centuries, traditional culture has been the inspiration for sustainable practices. In Sundarbans, *Itu puja* rituals show the way of returning to nature and securing a sustainable future. It is necessary to give importance to traditional cultures to conserve them and integrate them with modern technology to better implement building a sustainable world.

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